

Impact of Rural Development Programmes on Sustainable Productivity of Farmers in Rivers-East Senatorial District of Rivers State

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Abstract

The study was conducted to examine the impact of rural development programmes on sustainable productivity farmers in Rivers East senatorial District of Rivers State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three corresponding hypotheses were formulated. The population of the study was 597 (269 male and 328 female) farmers registered in FADAMA Cooperative in Rivers State. The sample size for the study was 249 (132 females and 117 males) farmers from 4 purposively selected Local Government Areas. A 45-item self-structured 4-point rating scale questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was validated and tested for reliability, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.70. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Furthermore, z-test was utilized in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that rural infrastructural programmes impacted on the productivity of the rural famers in the district. The provision of micro-credit facilities (loans, financial services, grants etc) by financial institutions, agricultural banks and social organizations, through the agriculture credit and Guarantee scheme improved farmers sustainable productivity of rural farmers. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst others, that Government and development agencies should strengthen rural infrastructure by investing in roads, irrigation systems, storage facilities, and rural electrification projects. Also, agricultural extension programmes should be scaled up with well-trained personnel, digital platforms, and demonstration farms. Finally, Government, through financial institutions and cooperative societies should provide farmers with affordable credit, low-interest loans, and flexible repayment plans for rural farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Keywords: Rural Development Programme, Sustainable Productivity, Farmers

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural productivity has been a subject of utmost concern due to its inevitable role to human existence. Agricultural productivity is measured on the ratio of agricultural outputs to inputs. It is as a measure of the efficiency of a system, person, machine, factory, etc.in converting inputs into useful outputs. Agricultural productivity consists of all the factors of production such as labour, capital farming experiences, availability and management of water and other biological factors that produced (output) with the number of inputs used to produce those goods and services. Agricultural productivity is measured in money produced per unit of land, but yields are measured in the weight of the crop produced per unit of land.

Agricultural productivity growth has led to drastic reductions in global poverty and food insecurity and continues to be a primary engine of growth in many parts of the world including Nigeria. Productivity growth in agriculture has the largest impact of any sector on poverty reduction. World Bank (2019) was of the opinion that continuing to make improvements to agricultural productivity, especially in low-income nations, is necessary to ensure sufficient food for an increasing global population and to traverse the last mile toward eliminating extreme poverty in developing nations. Two-thirds of the global extreme poor are located at the rural areas, and earn their livelihood from farming. The rural population represents an average of over 60 percent of the total population of Nigeria and about 90 percent of the rural labour force engaged directly or indirectly in agricultural production activities (in the area of small-scale farming) (World Bank, 2019); and given the large contribution of this sector to the overall economy, it seems obvious that agriculture should be a key component of growth and development in terms of sustainable farmers productivity to bring the rural dwellers out of poverty.

Agriculture, which is the main activity for livelihood for the rural dwellers, employs between 70% and 80% of the working population. Besides, local rural populations ensure food consumption from agricultural production, thereby guaranteeing household food security (World Bank, 2020). Thus,

making Nigeria depends on rural areas for most of their survival and development resources. However, in spite of this key role of rural areas in agriculture, they are confronted with severe problems, which retard their progress with consequent problems for survival of the local people.

Agriculture and rural developments are crucial for the structural transformation and economic development of Nigeria (Omeje & Ogbu, 2015). In line with this, emphasis has been on rural development by the federal, state and local governments in Nigeria. This is because; rural communities are the most important sector of the Nigerian economy, so long as agriculture is concerned. Rural development refers to the process of improving the quality of life and economic wellbeing of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. Thus, the need for rural development or transformation in Nigeria has spurred government at all levels to initiate various developmental efforts aimed at solving perennial problems of the rural areas. At different period, government has launched series of programmes to ensure better living for the rural dwellers especially to support rural farmers in their productivity.

Achieving rural development agenda in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State, will depend largely on the availability and access by the farm households to certain productivity resources and the extent to which these resources contribute to the wellbeing of those living in the rural areas. This is because the most of the country's population, resources particularly land, natural and mineral resources are in this area (Akanbi & Jnkayinfa, 2020). In addition, these resources serve as inputs in any productivity activity and include human resources, financial resources, natural resources, social resources, physical resources (Carney, 2019). These aforementioned resources are combined in varying magnitude in pursuit of different productivity strategies (agricultural or non-agricultural).

Rural infrastructures are critical for rural development, and key stimulants to agricultural development and growth. Increase in farmers productivity depends on good infrastructural facilities that serve as instruments to improve their economy. Rural infrastructure such as roads, electrification, storage facilities, and irrigation is essential for boosting agricultural productivity and facilitating economic transformation (Ghosal, in Amah, Oguanobi & Mgbemena, 2025). Emphasizing on the need for rural development, Olayiwola (2022) stated that they act as incentives, attracting industrial activities and investments by improving conditions in rural areas. Rural infrastructure development is the process of designing, financing, constructing, and maintaining the essential physical structures and networks (roads, energy systems, clean water, and digital connectivity) that are vital for economic growth, poverty reduction, and improving the quality of life in rural communities.

Reports by International Labour Organization (2010) revealed that the development of rural infrastructure gives a level playing field by providing rural populations with access to opportunities and services comparable to those in urban areas. This aligns with Emokaro and Ovoboh (2016) who in their study on the impact of the Community Driven Development and Social Development Project on the overall development farmers revealed that CDD and CSDP enhanced the lives of the rural people including farmers. Rural infrastructure helps rural farmer in their agricultural productivity level. The land productivity and production rise due to this infrastructure. Ajay, Roop and Meenakshi (2021) noted that the availability of proper water supply helps to increase productivity. Furthermore, the authors noted that electrification also helps to increase productivity.

Recent literature (Anderson & Shimokawa, 2016) indicates that rural infrastructural development significantly improves agricultural productivity in developing economies. Effective infrastructure has been described as a key foundation for strong economic growth that plays a critical role in ensuring efficient operations in the cassava value chain (Oni, 2013). Infrastructural facilities are basic services without which the needed environment as well as primary, secondary and tertiary

productive activities will not be able to function. Infrastructural facilities can be physical (such as roads, water, rural electrification, storage and processing facilities), social infrastructure (health and educational facilities, community centres, fire and security services) and institutional infrastructure (credit and financial institutions, agricultural research facilities) (Rahji, 2017). Availability of adequate infrastructure facilities is an important pre-requisite for sustainable economic and social development.

Various agricultural infrastructure needed for increased productivity includes Electricity- this plays an important role for the development of agriculture as most production equipment and machines run on electricity. But still many villages are either having shortages of electricity and even in some areas no electricity. Connectivity of the road also plays an important role in agriculture. 15% of agricultural produce has been lost in transportation of goods from farm gate to the proper place. Poor quality of roads in rural areas limits the trader from reaching the farmer and farmer to reach to the trader. Another agricultural infrastructure required for increased productivity is irrigation. Underutilization of irrigation is a serious problem; this system helps the farmer for water supply. Every activity needs to have finance. But many rural areas don't have sufficient financial institutions like banks. Many times, due to lack of money and funds, the farmers face problems like purchasing seeds, fuel for tractors, etc. So, the banks that provide the finance for the farmer should be started in rural areas.

Farmers in rural areas are facing a lot of problem with regards to improve productivity. This could be due to lack of technical know-how or knowledge on improved methods of production, lack of information dissemination through farming system extension services and agricultural programmes. Agricultural production has been a serious problem in the study area and in Nigeria in general. The application of agricultural extension services provides a very good development platform, for information which is sharing with regards to a larger number of people by the use of information delivery. Agricultural extension programmes have been the main conduit for disseminating information on farm technologies, support rural adult learning and assist farmers in developing their farm technical and managerial skills (Danso-Abbeam, Ehiakpor & Aidoo, 2018).

Agricultural extension services encompass a range of activities aimed at transferring agricultural knowledge, providing training and management practices, and disseminating useful agricultural research information to farmers, typically through a network of trained professionals. Agricultural extension programmes are used in collection with education to educate or train farmers on the methods required to achieve increased productivity. The programmes conducted outside the university were described as extension programmes. Anil, Prahlad, Rahul, Prasad, Rajesh, Abhishek, Manohar, and Nandini (2024) noted that these services are designed to assist farmers in increasing their productivity, managing their resources more efficiently, and improving their overall livelihoods. In Nigeria, these services have been a fundamental component of agricultural development strategies, seeking to bridge the gap between farmers and agricultural research institutions.

The expression connoted an extension of knowledge from the university to places and people far beyond. Abu harb, Dayoub and Al-Najjar (2024) described them as vital elements that offers farmers essential knowledge and modern technology to boost their productivity and crop quality. Agricultural extension services are essential in bridging the gap between research and actual farming to increase farm productivity and sustainability. These initiatives enhance farmers' skills, address challenges, and promote economic well-being, fostering sustainable development. By serving as platforms for knowledge transfer, these programs encourage modern practices and elevate productivity. Personalized technical guidance further aids farmers in improving farm management

and crop quality, contributing to overall agricultural sustainability (Kaliky et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023; Ferroni & Zhou, 2012).

To boost the sustainability and competitiveness in agricultural sector, Abu harb, et al, (2024) noted that essential measures must involve implementing extension programmes. These programmes provide sustainable technologies, financial support, and training to enhance farmers' management and marketing skills. It is expected that extension programmes will help increase farm productivity, farm revenue, reduce poverty and minimize food insecurity. Agricultural extension programmes significantly boost farmers' sustainable productivity by transferring knowledge and new technologies, leading to better farm management, increased yields, higher incomes, and improved technical efficiency. According to Ferroni and Zhou (2012), these services address critical areas like crop management, soil fertility, pest control, and access to market information, helping farmers make more informed decisions and adopt sustainable practices.

Agricultural development is necessary for poverty reduction and food security in Nigeria; however, the increase in agricultural productivity in the region has been slow due to lack of credit facilities for adoption of modern technologies. These have been identified as constraints to productivity of farmers. Rural farmers without sufficient collateral tend to be excluded from formal financial services, due to high transaction costs and imperfect information, which makes formal banks reluctant to offer services to them. As a consequence, poor farmers may be unable to invest in new technology or profitable income generating activities. It was in the light of this that Amadi and Aleru (2020) emphasized on the need for accessibility of zero-interest loan for rural farmers socio-economic empowerment.

In Rivers State, where agriculture is largely handled by rural farmers at subsistence level face particular challenges. Crops such as cassava, yam, and maize predominate, but production is often hampered by fragmented landholdings, reliance on rain-fed farming, rising input costs and limited loan access. These issues hinder productivity and, in most case, pose a threat to food security. In some cases, farmers note that formal loans (e.g. from the Bank of Agriculture) are much harder to obtain in the South-East than in other regions (Okojie, 2025). These show the need for improving financial inclusion, alongside investments in agricultural-related infrastructure and support services to boost agricultural productivity and household food security in Nigeria (Okon, et al., 2024).

Empirical evidence reports that digital microcredit significantly increased fish farm yields and farmers' incomes in Nigeria (Mukaila, 2024). These results suggest that when credit is effectively delivered, smallholder farmers can leverage microloans to enhance productivity and improve their livelihoods. According to Obiaocha and Matthews-Njoku (2017) availability of productive resources such as micro-credit had impact on the productivity of rural farmers in the Southeast of Nigeria. In the words of Ewuola (2018), micro-credit had great impact on the productivity of rural farmers in Edo State.

Statement of the Problem

Farmers who are responsible for the production of food are left unattended to, in terms of rural development; thus, they continue to grapple with low productivity, poor access to infrastructure, limited credit facilities, inadequate extension services, and environmental challenges that hinder sustainable agricultural practices. These problems could be based on the total neglect of rural areas and consequential pressures on the urban economy. Many rural dwellers due to low standard of living and poor lifestyle in the rural areas, lack access to functional hospitals and reportedly experienced illness, preventable diseases, and premature death among others. In addition, these areas

suffer during production, harvesting and post-harvest activities due to poor motorable farm roads, potable water and electricity.

The scarcity of these vital amenities could predispose farmers to the state of inactivity, illness and denied access to comfort. To address these constraints, governments in developing nations like Nigeria initiated appropriate policies and intensified development projects to enhance sustainable agricultural productivity among poor households in rural areas. Various rural development programmes were also initiated by non-governmental organizations, and international agencies with the aim of enhancing farmers' welfare, boosting agricultural output, and promoting rural transformation. In spite of the proliferation of programmes, there remains a glaring gap between policy intentions and actual outcomes in terms of sustainable productivity of farmers. Many farmers still operate at subsistence levels, with minimal adoption of modern technologies, inadequate market linkages, and persistent poverty. The inconsistent performance of these programmes raises critical questions about their effectiveness, implementation strategies, and sustainability. Hence, there is a need to critically investigate the impact of rural development programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of State Rivers.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of this study was to ascertain the impact of rural development programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the impact of rural infrastructural projects on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.
2. Assess the impact of agricultural extension programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.
3. Examine the impact of micro-credit facilities on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Research Questions

Based on the identified purpose of the study, the following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the impacts of rural infrastructural projects on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State?
2. What are the impacts of rural agricultural extension programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State?
3. What are the impacts of rural micro-credit facilities on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on the impact of rural infrastructural projects on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on impact of rural agricultural extension programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on impact of rural micro-credit facilities on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State of Nigeria. The district consists of eight Local Government Areas,

which include Emohua, Etche, Ikwerre, Obio-Akpor, Ogu-Bolo, Okirika, Omuma and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas. Agriculture is the major occupation of the inhabitants of the Local Government Areas. The practice of farming and fishing by the indigenes of the area is induced by their rich soil and body of water around the LGAs, which stretches from the southern to the Northern parts of the state. Subsistence farming is prevalent and about 75% of the population is engaged in it. Some of these areas are not really well developed despite been the food basket of the state.

The population of this study comprised of 597 (269 male and 328 female) registered farmers in Rivers-East Senatorial District of Rivers State (FADAMA Cooperative Associations' Register, 2019). The sample size for this study was 249 (132 females and 117 males) respondents using multistage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire (RDSPFQ) designed in 4-point rating scale of 'Agreement' to elicit information on the impact of rural development programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers. RDSPFQ was face and content validated by experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using test-retest method and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) which yielded a reliability index of 0.85. RDSPFQ was administered to the respondents by the researcher and with the help of two assistants. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation; while the z-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Item statement with mean values ≥ 2.50 were regarded as agreed, while those < 2.50 were regarded as disagreed. Furthermore, the null hypothesis with z-calculated less than z-critical of 1.96 was accepted, while those greater than or equal to 1.96 were rejected.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are the impacts of rural infrastructural programmes on the sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Responses on the Impact of Rural Infrastructural Programmes on Sustainable Productivity of Farmers in Rivers-East Senatorial District

S/N	Item Statements	Female Farmers = 132			Male Farmers = 117		
		Mea n	SD	Rmrk	Mea n	SD	Rmrk
1	The provision of farm to market roads improved farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.34	0.81	Agree	3.07	0.90	Agree
2	Provision of water supply improved farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.36	0.54	Agree	3.00	0.73	Agree
3	Construction of irrigation and canals improved farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.57	0.68	Agree	3.87	0.49	Agree
4	Good storage facilities will improve farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.02	0.81	Agree	3.44	0.61	Agree
5	Provision of railway lines improved farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.12	0.77	Agree	3.61	0.79	Agree
6	Good power supply improved farmers sustainable productivity;	3.19	0.84	Agree	3.52	0.63	Agree
7	Construction of bridges improved farmers sustainable productivity.	3.22	0.94	Agree	3.60	0.74	Agree
8	Good health facilities will improve farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.14	0.71	Agree	3.53	0.67	Agree
Grand Mean		3.12			3.33		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 revealed that all the item statements were agreed by the responses of the respondents. Table 1 revealed that the provision of farm to market roads improved farmers' sustainable productivity had mean score of (3.34 & 3.07), provision of water supply improved farmers' sustainable productivity (3.36 & 3.60), construction of irrigation and canals improved farmers' sustainable productivity (3.56 & 3.87), storage facilities improved farmers' sustainable productivity (3.02 & 3.44), provision of railway lines improved farmers' sustainable productivity (3.12 & 3.61), good power supply improved farmers sustainable productivity (3.19 & 3.52) construction of bridges improved farmers sustainable productivity (3.22 & 3.60), good health facilities improved farmers' sustainable productivity (3.14 & 3.55). The closeness of the standard deviation of male and female farmers showed that the respondents were close in their opinion.

Research Question 2: What are the impacts of agricultural extension programmes on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Responses on the Impact of Agricultural Extension Programmes on Sustainable Productivity of Farmers in Rivers-East Senatorial District

S/N	Item Statements	Female Farmers = 132			Male Farmers = 117		
		Mea n	SD	Rmrk	Mea n	SD	Rmrk
1.	Educating farmers on trends in agriculture sustains farmer's skills and food sufficiency	3.24	0.77	Agree	3.20	0.62	Agree
2.	Farmer education helps farmers become aware of improved skills for farming	3.04	0.89	Agree	3.10	1.06	Agree
3.	Introducing farmers to new crop and animal species boost production capacity of farmers	3.12	0.94	Agree	3.17	0.99	Agree
4.	Practical training on pest and disease as well as soil management helped to cushion the effect of loss in the productivity of crops in the zone	3.34	0.71	Agree	3.29	0.73	Agree
5.	Training on farm management reduces farmer's cost of production	3.07	1.07	Agree	3.02	1.19	Agree
6.	Quality non-formal education of farmers enhances productivity and production efficiency	3.23	0.54	Agree	3.02	1.08	Agree
7.	Introducing farmers to new farm input promotes farm productivity which in turn boost farmers economic livelihood	3.04	1.03	Agree	3.16	1.06	Agree
Grand Mean		2.64			2.77		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 revealed that educating farmers on trends in agriculture sustains farmers' skills and food sufficiency, had mean score of (3.24 & 3.20), farmer education helps farmers become aware of improved skills for farming, (3.04 & 3.10), introducing farmers to new crop and animals pieces boost production capacity of farmers (3.12 & 3.17), practical training on pest and disease management as well as soil management helped to cushion the effect of loss in the productivity of crops in the zone, (3.34 & 3.29), training on farm management reduces farmers cost of production (3.07 & 3.02), quality non-formal education of farmers enhances productivity and production efficiency (3.23 & 3.02), introducing farmers to new farm input promotes farm productivity which in turn boost farmers economic livelihood (3.04 & 3.16). The closeness of the standard deviation of male and female farmers showed that the respondents were close in their opinion.

Research Question 3: What are the impact of micro-credit facilities on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Responses of Micro-credit Facilities on Sustainable Productivity of Farmers in Rivers-East Senatorial District of Rivers State

S/ N	Items	Female Farmers = 132			Male Farmers = 117		
		Mea n	SD	Rmrk	Mea n	SD	Rmrk
1.	Farmers' cooperative organizations promote farmers agricultural business;	3.24	0.72	Agree	3.27	1.02	Agree
2.	Credit and savings scheme help farmers to meet their daily needs;	3.08	1.06	Agree	3.00	1.07	Agree
3.	Increased access to financial services improved farmers' sustainable productivity.	3.44	0.69	Agree	3.20	1.06	Agree
4.	Provision of credit /loans to farmers improved income levels and alleviated poverty.	3.18	0.84	Agree	3.27	0.81	Agree
5.	Agricultural loan programme boosts farmers in their agricultural business and increase income	3.74	0.61	Agree	3.39	0.53	Agree
6.	Subsidy programmes for farmers encouraged commercialization of farm product which alleviated poverty among farmers.	3.27	0.77	Agree	3.42	0.89	Agree
7.	The provision of credit facilities by financial institutions reduced the cost of capital-intensive technology and assets relative to family labour.	3.03	1.00	Agree	3.42	0.78	Agree
8.	Farmers' cooperative support farmers during financial crisis.	3.09	0.63	Agree	3.26	0.56	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.13			3.25		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 revealed that farmers' cooperative organizations promotes farmers agricultural business (3.24 & 3.37), credit and savings scheme help farmers to meet their daily needs (3.08 & 3.00), increased access to financial services improved farmers' sustainable productivity (3.44 & 3.20), provision of credit/loans to farmers improved income levels and alleviated poverty (3.18 & 3.27), agricultural loan programme boost farmers in their agricultural business and increase income; (3.27 & 3.42), subsidy programmes for farmers encouraged commercialization of farm product which alleviated poverty among farmers (3.74 & 3.89), the provision of credit facilities by financial institutions reduced the cost of capital-intensive technology (3.03 & 3.42), and Farmers' cooperative support farmers during financial crisis. (3.09 & 3.25), with a grand mean of (3.13 & 3.25) respectively. Also, the closeness of the standard deviation of male and female farmers showed that the respondents were close in their opinion.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on impacts of rural infrastructural projects/programmes on their sustainable productivity in Rivers-East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis on Mean Responses of Male and Female Farmers on Impact of Rural Infrastructural Projects on their Sustainable Productivity in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Group	n	Mean	SD	Df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Female farmers	132	3.12	0.82	247	0.05	-2.33	1.96	Accept H ₀
Male farmers	117	3.33	0.70					

Result in Table 4 revealed that the z calculated value (-2.33) is less than z-crit value (1.96). Thus, the study deduced that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on the impact of rural infrastructural programmes on their sustainable productivity in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on the impact of agricultural extension programmes on their sustainable productivity in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Table 5: Z-test Analysis of Male and Female Farmers on the Impact of Agricultural Extension Programmes on their Sustainable Productivity in Rivers-East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Group	n	Mean	SD	Df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Female farmers	132	2.64	1.00	247	0.05	0.16	1.96	Accept H ₀
Male farmers	117	2.77	1.03					

Table 5 revealed that z-calculated value obtained (0.16) is less than the critical level of z (1.96). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted; and thus, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on the impact of agricultural extension programmes on their sustainable productivity in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on impact of micro - credit facilities on their sustainable productivity in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis on the Mean Scores of Male and Female Farmers on the Impact of Micro-credit Facilities on their Sustainable Productivity in Rivers East Senatorial Zone of Rivers State.

Group	n	Mean	SD	Df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Female farmers	132	3.13	0.79	247	0.05	1.03	1.96	Accept H ₀
Male farmers	117	3.25	0.84					

Result from Table 6: revealed that the z-calculated value obtained (1.03) is less than the z-critical level of 1.96. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female farmers on the impact of micro-credit facilities on sustainable productivity of farmers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State was accepted.

Discussion of Results

Table 1 revealed that accessible roads from farm-to-market, provision of water supply, construction of irrigation and canals, good educational system, provision of railway lines, good power supply, construction of bridges, and good health system improved farmers' sustainable productivity. Also, from the null hypothesis in Table 4.6 revealed that the mean responses of male and female farmers on the impact of rural infrastructural programmes on their sustainable productivity did not significantly differ. The findings of the study align with Gbolagade, et al, (2015) who in a study on

effect of rural infrastructural programmes on the productivity of the vulnerable groups reported that FADAMA III programmes impacted positively on the lives of the rural farmers in Kwara State. The findings also agree with Emokaro and Ovoboh (2016) who evaluated the impact of the community driven development (CDD) and social development project (CSDP) in meeting the overall development farmers revealed that these programmes (CDD and CSDP) enhanced the lives of the rural people including farmers.

Table 2 revealed that educating farmers on trends in agriculture sustains farmers' skills and food sufficiency, farmer education to help farmers become aware of improved skills for farming, introducing farmers to new crop and animal species boost production capacity of farmers, practical training on pest and disease management as well as soil management, and education on new farm input promotes farmers' sustainable productivity. The findings of the study are in conformity with Ferroni and Zhou (2012) who posited that extension services address critical areas like crop management, soil fertility, pest control, and access to market information that help farmers make more informed decisions and adopt sustainable practices. Furthermore, the findings are in line with Abu harb, et al, (2024) who in a study noted that the implementation of agricultural extension programmes in rural communities help in the provision of sustainable technologies, financial support, and training to enhance farmers' management and marketing skills.

Table 3 revealed that farmers' cooperative organizations promotes agribusiness, credit and savings scheme help farmers to meet their daily needs, increased access to financial services improved farmers' sustainable productivity, provision of credit/loans to farmers improved income levels and alleviated poverty, agricultural loan programme boost farmers in their agricultural business and increase income, subsidy programmes for farmers encouraged commercialization of farm product which alleviated poverty among farmers, and credit facilities by financial institutions reduced the cost of capital-intensive technology. The findings are in agreement with Obiaocha and Matthews-Njoku (2017) who in a study to assess the implication of resources available to rural households for agricultural and rural development productive in South-east Nigeria discovered that productive resources such as micro-credit had great impact on the productivity capacity of rural farmers in the Southeast of Nigeria. The finding is also inconsonant with the assertion of Ewuola (2018) that micro-credit had great impact on the productivity of rural farmers in Edo State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that rural development programmes have in a long run improved the standard of productivity of rural farmers. Nevertheless, achieving rural development agenda in rural areas in Nigeria will depend largely on the availability, access of the farm households to certain livelihood resources and the extent to which these resources contribute to the well-being of those living in the rural areas. This is because the bulk of the country's population, resources particularly land, natural and mineral resources are in this area. In addition, these resources serve as inputs in any livelihood activity and include infrastructural facilities, health facilities, job creation programmes, financial resources and social welfare resources. These aforementioned resources are combined in varying magnitude in pursuit of different livelihood strategies (agricultural or non-agricultural).

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and development agencies should strengthen rural infrastructure by investing in roads, irrigation systems, storage facilities, and rural electrification. This will reduce post-harvest losses, enhance market access, and promote the adoption of modern farming technologies, thereby increasing farmers' productivity.

2. Agricultural extension programmes should be scaled up with well-trained personnel, digital platforms, and demonstration farms. Continuous training in climate-smart agriculture, improved seed varieties, pest management, and sustainable practices will enable rural farmers to apply modern knowledge for increased output.
3. Government, through financial institutions and cooperative societies should provide farmers with affordable credit, low-interest loans, and flexible repayment plans. Access to micro-credit will empower rural farmers to invest in high-yielding seeds, fertilizers, mechanization, and value addition technologies, leading to sustainable productivity growth.

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